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**A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF DEEP
LEARNING APPLICATIONS AND ADVANCES IN
CROP DEMAND FORECASTING**

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Abstract:- This comprehensive analysis explores the widespread use of deep learning (DL) techniques as well as recent advances in crop forecasting. With agriculture facing rising challenges from climate change, population increase, and market volatility, accurate and timely crop yield forecast is critical to guaranteeing food security and sustainable agricultural practices. The paper encompasses the use of deep learning approaches in many aspects of agricultural forecasting, including yield prediction, disease detection, and market price forecasting. It integrates findings from a variety of studies to assess the efficacy, scalability, and practical implications of DL-based techniques in agricultural settings. The study analyses significant research initiatives to identify new trends, difficulties, and possibilities in DL-driven crop forecasting. It also examines the use of many data sources to improve prediction accuracy and reliability. Furthermore, the review investigates the potential of DL models to aid decision-making processes for farmers, policymakers, and stakeholders throughout the agricultural value chain. This review's comprehensive analysis and synthesis of existing literature seeks to provide insights into the current state-of-the-art in DL applications for crop forecasting, as well as to guide future research paths in this important topic.

Keywords:- crop forecasting, deep learning, yield prediction, decision-making, Sustainable Agriculture, Agricultural Applications.

1. Introduction

Agriculture plays a crucial role in the Indian economy, as crops such as rice, wheat, cotton, and maize are of vital importance. Many people in India heavily rely on agriculture as they are primary source of income. Among these crops, maize stands out due to its high productivity and its significance as a primary energy source for human consumption. However, the yield of maize crops can be negatively impacted by various diseases that affect the plant leaves, ultimately affecting overall production levels [1]. Price shocks in the agricultural sector have significant implications for farmers' incomes and food security. So, it is essential to understand and predict these fluctuations, particularly for key global agricultural commodities [2]. In developing countries, there is a strong demand for accurate and timely monitoring of maize yield using Satellite Imagery. This task is further complicated by the challenge of spatial heterogeneity, which is especially noticeable in China's vast territories [3]. Similarly, in Indonesia, maize is a critical food crop. Malang Regency, one of the major producers, ranks 10th in corn production in East Java. The high demand for maize in this region emphasizes its numerous benefits and the interest of local farmers in cultivating it [4].

Maize plays a crucial role in the global food supply. In order to cultivate and market maize effectively, precise seed sorting is necessary. However, traditional methods of identifying seed varieties are often inefficient, time-consuming, and prone to damage [5]. The economic importance of agriculture is widespread, but climate change is increasingly impacting this sector, leading to food insecurities. Extreme weather conditions caused by climate change have a negative effect on crop yields and agricultural productivity [6]. Estimating the performance of crop yields is a significant area of interest, particularly in breeding programs where it is impractical to test all possible hybrids resulting from parent crossings due to time and cost constraints [7]. Accurately predicting crop yields is a major challenge in agriculture and is essential for making well-informed decisions at the national, provincial, and regional levels to meet food demands. To forecast crop production, various factors such as soil conditions, meteorological conditions, environmental factors, and crop variables are taken into consideration [8].

Rice is an important global food crop that requires a significant amount of water, highlighting the importance of water management for sustainable production. However, there is limited data available on water use in rice irrigation [9]. Consequently, predicting crop yield has become a prominent area of research, which involves considering environmental, soil, water, and crop parameters. To enhance the accuracy of yield predictions, deep learning models are increasingly utilized to extract relevant crop features [10]. In light of these challenges and advancements, this study provides a comprehensive review of deep learning applications and recent advances in crop forecasting. Its goal is to consolidate existing research, identify trends, address challenges, and explore the potential of DL-driven techniques in improving agricultural forecasting. Through these efforts, the study aims to contribute to food security and promote sustainable agricultural practices.

2. Existing Methods

Recent endeavours in crop demand forecasting have seen the integration of advanced machine learning algorithms and big data analytics to improve accuracy and scalability. These methodologies leverage diverse datasets, including market trends, consumer behaviour,

and environmental factors, to predict crop demand dynamics with greater precision. However, challenges persist in ensuring data quality, model interpretability, and adapting to rapidly changing market conditions.

2.1. Analysis of demand forecasting of agriculture using machine learning algorithm

Chelliah et al (2024) proposed a methodology that addresses the critical issue of predicting agricultural drought. The aim is to mitigate the severe impacts it has on human life and agricultural productivity. The system utilizes machine learning algorithms and Satellite

Imagery, specifically Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), for accurate forecasting. The process includes data collection, supervised learning, and optimization testing, resulting in up to 96 percent accuracy in predicting drought. By automating data entries and predictions through user-friendly applications and voice chatbot mechanisms, the system enhances efficiency and transparency in agricultural operations. Integration with the banking sector allows for standardized data records, easy access to insurance, and loan schemes, which help farmers manage risks. The flow diagram of the proposed system is illustrated in Figure. 1.

Figure1. proposed CNN flow diagram

Agricultural market analysis reveals insights into input and output market dynamics, which help farmers and stakeholders make decisions. Discussions about risk assessment emphasize the necessity of commercialization and organizational methods to handle market issues. The system encourages innovation in traditional farming operations and provides viable solutions for increasing agricultural revenue and resilience. Finally, this strategy aids to informed decision-making, increasing agricultural sustainability and production in the face of climate-related difficulties.

2.2. Crop-yield and price forecasting using machine learning

Mulla et al (2020) aim to develop a comprehensive system for predicting crop yield and prices, which is essential for farmers in agricultural economies like India. The system intends to provide farmers with accurate yield estimates based on rainfall and the Wholesale Price Index (WPI), using machine learning. It also aims to forecast future market prices by considering past crop prices and sowing months, extending these predictions nationwide for the next year. The methodology involves using tree algorithms for efficient prediction, leveraging datasets on crop details and rainfall. The proposed system consists of four key implementation modules: Data Acquisition, Data Exploration, Machine Learning Prediction, and Web Application. In the Data Acquisition module, crop data is collected from public repositories, with a focus on rainfall data. The Data Exploration module involves essential pre-processing steps, such as Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA) techniques like descriptive statistics and visualization. The Machine Learning Prediction module includes data partitioning, algorithm definition (e.g., Decision Tree Algorithm), training, testing, and updating the user interface with calculated values. The Decision Tree Algorithm, chosen for its interpretability and applicability to a wide range of tasks, plays a pivotal role in predicting crop yields and prices is illustrated in figure 2.

Figure 2. Architecture diagram of the proposed system

The proposed framework is tested for its ability to predict crop yield, increase or decrease trends, and market prices. Figures are used to show the top gaining and losing crops, crop exploration throughout seasons, and predicted yield and price patterns for individual crops over the following year. The system's conclusions emphasize its usefulness in assisting farmers' decision-making processes, as well as its potential for widespread adoption. The Decision Tree Algorithm demonstrates promising accuracy and offers useful insights into crop selection and management procedures.

2.3. District wise price forecasting of wheat in Pakistan using deep learning

Rasheed et al (2021) conducted a research study that focuses on developing an advanced neural network system for forecasting wheat prices in various districts of Pakistan. The study utilizes Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models and compares them with other machine learning time series techniques. The research process begins with the acquisition of a wheat price dataset, which is then split into training and test datasets for pre-processing. To prepare the data for prediction by machine and deep learning algorithms, a Moving Average Filter (MA Filter) is applied to smooth the raw data. The dataset is then used to train and evaluate different models, with error performance measured using Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE). The study proposes four unique cases for predicting wheat prices: one-month prediction with price data, one-month prediction with all features, one-year prediction with price data, and one-year prediction with all features is shown in figure 3. Each case involves training models on Bagged Trees, Gaussian Process Regression (GPR), Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA), and LSTM algorithms, and testing on both raw and

smoothed data.

Figure 3. Flow of the proposed work

The results indicate that the LSTM model outperforms other techniques in terms of prediction accuracy, especially when trained on smoothed data. The study also compares its approach with previous works, highlighting the advantages of predicting monthly prices over yearly

values and focusing on district-level variations. The proposed system offers significant improvements in prediction errors compared to existing methods, providing valuable insights for policymakers and stakeholders in Pakistan's agricultural sector. Ultimately, this study contributes to enhancing economic studies and policy-making by providing more accurate and timely predictions of wheat prices, thereby increasing confidence in decision-making processes.

2.4. Crop yield estimation using deep learning based on climate big data and irrigation scheduling

In this study, Alibabaei et al. (2021) proposed an end-to-end decision support system for irrigation scheduling in agricultural settings. The objective was to develop a model capable of accurately predicting crop yields based on various environmental factors, including temperature, humidity, wind speed, evapo-transpiration, soil moisture, irrigation, and precipitation. The proposed system flow involved collecting data from an agricultural weather station in Portugal and pre-processing the collected data to address missing values, normalize the data, and remove multicollinear parameters. The data were then used to train deep learning models, specifically Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory (BLSTM) networks, which were chosen for their ability to capture temporal dependencies in the data.

Figure 4. proposed LSTM and GRU structures

The models were trained using a combination of historical climate data and simulated crop yields from a crop growth model is shown in figure 4. Dropout and early stopping techniques were utilized to prevent over fitting during training. The performance of the models was evaluated using mean square error (MSE) and (R^2) score metrics. The results demonstrated that the BLSTM models outperformed other deep learning architectures, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Multilayer Perceptrons (MLP), as well as traditional machine learning algorithms like Random Forest (RF). The proposed system exhibited promising results in predicting crop yields under different irrigation regimes, offering valuable insights for optimizing irrigation schedules to maximize productivity while minimizing water usage.

2.5. Deep Yield: A combined convolutional neural network with long short-term memory for crop yield forecasting

In the fourth study, Gavahi et al (2021) aimed to develop an efficient system called DeepYield for forecasting crop yields using a combination of ConvLSTM and 3DCNN architectures is illustrated in figure 5. Their objective was to improve the accuracy of crop yield predictions at the county level across the CONUS by incorporating spatial and temporal information from MODIS Satellite Imagery.

Figure 5. ConvLSTM and 3DCNN network architectures

The proposed system involved pre-processing MODIS data, including Surface Reflectance (SR) and Land Surface Temperature (LST), to create 4D tensors representing spatiotemporal features. These tensors were then inputted into both ConvLSTM and 3DCNN networks for comprehensive feature extraction. The models were extensively tested and compared against other methods, such as Decision Trees, CNN+GP, and CNN-LSTM. The results demonstrated the superior performance of DeepYield in accurately forecasting soybean yields for the years 2018 and 2019. Furthermore, the study emphasized the potential benefits of this approach for agricultural planning and decision-making, providing valuable insights for farmers and governmental agencies like the USDA involved in regional and national crop yield forecasting.

2.6.Satellite-based soybean yield forecast: Integrating machine learning and weather data for improving crop yield prediction in southern Brazil

Schwalbert et al (2021) conducted a study aimed at developing a robust system to forecast soybean yields in the northern region of Rio Grande do Sul (RS) state, Brazil. The focus was on utilizing historical municipality-level yield data and Satellite Imagery, specifically vegetation indices (VIs) and weather variables, to enhance yield predictions is illustrated in figure 6.

Figure 6 Flowchart of model development

The selection of this region was based on its high frequency of soybean cultivation and significant cropland area. Historical yield data from 2003 to 2016 was obtained from IBGE, while Satellite data, including NDVI and EVI from MODIS, along with land surface temperature (LST) and precipitation, were acquired from NASA EOSDIS and CHIRPS datasets. An important aspect of their approach was the use of cloud-free Satellite mosaics, which were crucial for accurate data retrieval. The data collection process involved merging shapefiles from the Cadastro Ambiental Rural (CAR) system to define cropland boundaries. Subsequently, remote sensing and weather data were organized at the municipality level and combined with yield data for model development. The researchers employed multivariate OLS regression, random forest, and LSTM neural networks to establish empirical relationships between yield and predictors. The performance of the models was evaluated using leave-one-year-out cross-validation, with metrics such as MAE, MSE, and RMSE. Additionally, a time series sensitivity analysis was conducted to assess the impact of

forecasting at different stages of the growing season. The results of the study showed that the LSTM neural network consistently outperformed other algorithms, with seasonal integrated predictors producing the best results. Furthermore, a regression analysis of long-term yield and weather data anomalies provided insights into the likelihood of extreme events. Overall, the study presented a comprehensive framework for soybean yield forecasting, integrating remote sensing, weather data, and machine learning techniques to enhance predictive accuracy and facilitate agricultural decision-making in the region.

2.7. Development and Evaluation of a Deep Learning Based System to Predict District-Level Maize Yields in Tanzania

Tende et al (2023) developed the Maize Yield Prediction System (MYPS) to forecast end-of-season maize yields for districts in Tanzania. They collected data from rural farmers and government officers in Kyimo ward, Mbeya region, Tanzania, focusing on functional and non-functional requirements. Due to the COVID-19 pandemic, a survey was conducted by a research assistant, covering 30 maize farmers and 5 cooperative union officers. The system's key feature was the ability to predict maize yields through SMS and a web interface. The system design followed a three-tier architecture, allowing SMS queries to trigger deep learning models for yield prediction is illustrated in figure 7.

Figure 7 Architecture of unimodal and bimodal deep learning models

Deep learning models, based on LSTM networks, were trained using time-series data including NDVI, climate data, and historical maize yields. Hyper parameter tuning experiments were conducted using K-fold cross-validation, resulting in the determination of optimal model configurations. Testing revealed promising results, with the unimodal and bimodal deep learning models achieving MAPE scores of 3.656% and 6.648%, respectively, on test datasets. These results demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed models for predicting maize yields. The system's accessibility through SMS was highlighted as a significant advantage, ensuring that even users without internet access could benefit from yield predictions. Overall, the study contributed a completed and ready-to-use deep learning-based system for maize yield prediction in Tanzania. The novel use of SMS for querying deep learning models and the comprehensive dataset covering almost all districts in Tanzania were notable achievements. Future work will focus on deploying MYPS to Tanzanian farmers and evaluating its usability and effectiveness.

2.8. Topdressing nitrogen demand prediction in rice crop using machine learning systems

In a study conducted by Iatrou et al. (2021) on a 110-hectare rice farm in Greece, a machine learning system was developed to predict topdressing nitrogen demands based solely on soil and Satellite data. By leveraging open-source Satellite data, limited field surveys for soil sampling, and machinery records, the model provided timely and comprehensive recommendations to the grower. This aided in better understanding fertility issues within the

area's soils. The main objective of the study was to construct a predictive model for topdressing nitrogen demands. However, it also achieved secondary goals, such as mapping inundated rice fields to indicate seeding dates a critical variable in the prediction process is shown in figure 8.

Figure 8 flow diagram of prediction process

To optimize yield prediction accuracy, the model utilized a combination of machine learning algorithms. The proposed system workflow involved data ingestion, zone delineation, soil sampling, inundation mapping, seeding date determination, LNC mapping, variable-rate fertilization, yield mapping, and finally, modelling using machine learning algorithms. Through meticulous data preparation and model configuration, the XGBoost algorithm emerged as the most suitable for the dataset, outperforming other tested models. The results showed that the model significantly reduced prediction errors, particularly when incorporating growth stage and LNC parameters. Additionally, by analyzing feature importance, the study shed light on the influence of soil properties on yield variance, with phosphorus and potassium deficiencies being particularly highlighted. Overall, the study demonstrated the efficacy of machine learning systems in precision agriculture. It offered a data-driven approach to optimize fertilization practices, improve yield prediction accuracy, and address fertility issues within agricultural soils.

2.9. Crop yield forecasting using data mining

The focus of Kamath et al (2021) is on using machine learning algorithms, specifically Random Forest, to predict crop yields Wheat price dataset. It starts with collecting data from official government websites. The agricultural dataset includes attributes such as state name, district name, humidity, temperature, and yield. The dataset is pre-processed to remove redundant data and normalize information. Then, the dataset is divided into training and testing sets to evaluate the model. The Random Forest algorithm, a type of supervised learning, is used to classify and predict crop yields based on historical data. The model is trained using scikit-learn in a Jupyter notebook environment. Predictions can be made on new

input data using the trained model. The model is saved in pickle format for future use in yield prediction. Evaluation metrics, specifically accuracy, show that the model performs well with a 98% accuracy rate.

Figure 9 block diagram of crop yield forecasting

Comparative analysis with other models like XGBoost, KNN, and logistic regression highlights the superiority of Random Forest in yield prediction. To make it user-friendly, a web-based interface is designed with four modules: Crop, Soil, Weather, and Predict. These modules allow users to explore crop and soil information, get live weather forecasts, and predict crop yields based on selected parameters. Data visualization techniques like pair plots and joint plots help understand the dataset, identify patterns, and trends. The system provides a graphical representation of actual versus predicted yield values to assess model performance. In summary, the proposed system offers a strong framework for predicting crop yields, providing valuable insights for farmers to optimize agricultural practices and reduce losses. By bridging the gap between technology and agriculture, the system contributes to sustainable farming and resource optimization. Future work includes scaling the model to predict yields for larger areas and addressing current limitations to enhance its applicability.

2.10. Estimation and forecasting of rice yield using phenology-based algorithm and linear regression model on sentinel-ii Satellite data

Nazir et al. (2021) explores the accurate quantification of rice yield and the identification of critical growth stages that influence production. The study employs Partial Least Square Regression (PLSR) in conjunction with time series vegetation indices to achieve precise yield predictions. Among the indices examined, NDVI emerges as the top performer, closely followed by EVI, SAVI, and REP.

Figure 10, Flow chart of rice yield forecasting

Through PLSR coefficients, the study highlights pivotal growth stages for yield, particularly the late vegetative, reproductive (panicle, flowering, milky), and ripening phases. These identified stages, consistent across all vegetation indices, emphasize their crucial role in estimating yield is illustrated in figure 10. The integration of PLSR and vegetation indices facilitates strategic decision-making concerning yield import/export and enables timely interventions for farmers. By providing actionable insights to farmers, such as optimal water, fertilizer, and pesticide usage, the study contributes to enhancing production efficiency. Furthermore, these findings are significant for policymakers as they inform the development of targeted policies aimed at addressing food security challenges. Ultimately, the outcomes of the study align with Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) such as hunger alleviation, poverty reduction, and land/food security. By promoting sustainable agricultural practices and fostering socio-economic development, the research underscores the importance of data-driven approaches in tackling global challenges.

2.11. Recommendation system for farmers using demand forecasting

Shashidhar. M et al (2021) conducted a study on forecasting onion demand in the Mumbai wholesale market. They utilized a seasonal ARIMA model and obtained data from the AGMARKNET website, covering the period from January 1, 2008, to August 30, 2010. The data was divided into training, validation, and test sets to ensure accurate predictions in out-of-sample periods. The training set spanned from January 1, 2008, to June 30, 2010, while the validation and test periods were in July and August 2010, respectively. The analysis began by identifying the model using the Box-Jenkins methodology. This involved determining the order of differencing, auto-regressive, and moving average components through examination of ACF and PACF plots. The optimal ARIMA model was selected, taking into account the seasonal patterns observed in the data, particularly the weekly demand peaks on Mondays.

Figure 11. Flow chart for weather prediction

The estimation of the model included assessing the significance of the parameters and ensuring they met the requirements of stationarity and invertibility is shown in figure 11. Three models were evaluated: ARIMA (1,0,0)x(1,1,0)₇, ARIMA (2,0,1)x(2,1,1)₇, and ARIMA (2,0,1). Based on statistical checks, Model A was identified as the most suitable. The accuracy of the model was validated using the first out-of-sample phase to ensure its reliability. Diagnostic tests confirmed the randomness and normality of the residuals, indicating a good fit. This forecasting model is useful for strategic decision-making in supply chain management, inventory optimization, and market stability. It benefits various stakeholders, from farmers to policymakers, and emphasizes the importance of robust statistical methods in improving agricultural market efficiency and addressing food security challenges.

2.12. *Improvement of crop production using recommender system by weather forecasts*

Kamatchi, S. et al (2019) aims to develop an advanced weather prediction model using Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) to enhance agricultural productivity and provide early disaster warnings. The model utilizes a three-year weather dataset from UCI, which includes variables such as barometric pressure, humidity, wind, sun brightness, and temperature. Pre-processing steps are taken to ensure high-quality input through data cleaning, selection, and transformation. Genetic algorithms are used to identify critical weather attributes, improving prediction accuracy. ANN models, known for their robustness in recognizing complex patterns, predict weather variables like temperature and humidity. The model's performance is refined through techniques such as back propagation and gradient descent to minimize errors. By analyzing historical weather data with time series methods, the ANN can identify and learn patterns, enhancing its predictive capability. Additionally, a hybrid recommender system that combines case-based reasoning and collaborative filtering provides crop recommendations based on predicted weather conditions and user preferences. This approach addresses issues of data scarcity and increases recommendation accuracy. The model also examines the relationship between weather variables and crop revenue by analyzing temperature and rainfall distributions over growing seasons, predicting the impact of weather on agricultural productivity is shown in figure 12.

Figure 12 flow diagram of agricultural productivity and early disaster warnings

Results indicate that the ANN model outperforms other techniques, achieving 93% accuracy in weather prediction with a 0.95 error rate, while the hybrid recommender system demonstrates a high accuracy of 96%. These findings confirm the model's effectiveness in forecasting weather and offering reliable crop recommendations, thereby supporting agricultural decision-making and disaster preparedness.

2.13. *Machine learning for demand forecasting in the physical internet: a case study of agricultural products in Thailand*

Kantasa-Ard et al (2021) proposed a research methodology that addresses key issues through a structured approach consisting of three main components. First, they developed an effective forecasting model to manage demand fluctuations and ensure proper resource planning across the supply chain. This was accomplished by using a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) Recurrent Neural Network implemented in Python, with the help of Keras and Sci-kit libraries. Second, to enhance the forecasting model's performance, they employed a hybrid metaheuristic approach that combined Genetic Algorithm (GA) and Scatter Search for automated parameter tuning. This optimization process focused on hyper parameters such as hidden layers and neural units. Third, they conducted a simulation of a Physical Internet network using the NetLogo multi-agent platform to evaluate resource planning and analyze the impact on holding and transportation costs.

The forecasting model followed a five-step process:

Data Gathering, Data Pre-processing, model implementation, forecast computation, and model evaluation. The data was normalized and divided into training (80%) and test (20%) sets, which were then used to predict demand using the LSTM model. Performance metrics such as RMSE, MAE, MAPE, and R-squared were applied to evaluate the model's performance. The hybrid metaheuristic approach significantly reduced the RMSE and MAPE scores, thereby enhancing efficiency. In order to test the effectiveness of the forecasted data in reducing supply chain costs, a simulation model was configured with five nodes. The simulation assumed equal daily demand orders and sufficient stock levels at hubs. By comparing the forecasted and real demand, the simulation demonstrated the effectiveness of the proposed approach in resource planning. The results indicated that the hybrid metaheuristic for LSTM provided superior accuracy and efficiency, thus validating its application for improving production and distribution planning in a Physical Internet network.

2.14. *Data analytics in the supply chain management: Review of machine learning applications in demand forecasting*

Aamer et al (2021) proposed a comprehensive methodology for forecasting rainfall and recommending suitable crop varieties in the Sleman District agricultural sector. The research process began with a literature review to understand the sector's issues. Data collection was then carried out from primary and secondary sources, including crop harvest and rainfall data from multiple years. The collected data underwent pre-processing and normalization to ensure its validity and feasibility for further analysis. For rainfall forecasting, two methods, Moving Average and Naive Bayes, were utilized. Each method offered distinct advantages in handling time series data and classification tasks. The Moving Average method, specifically the second approach, showed promising results in predicting future rainfall levels,

demonstrating its effectiveness in agricultural planning. On the other hand, the Naive Bayes classification algorithm was used to recommend crop varieties based on factors such as rainfall, pests, and production data from previous years. This algorithm proved to be robust in classifying crop yields, providing valuable insights for decision-making regarding crop selection. Experimental results validated the proposed methodologies, highlighting their usefulness in enhancing agricultural planning and decision support systems. Overall, the study presented an efficient approach to address agricultural challenges through data-driven forecasting and classification techniques, offering actionable recommendations for optimizing crop selection and resource allocation in the Sleman District agricultural sector.

2.15. *Rainfall forecasting to recommend crops varieties using moving average and naive bayes methods*

Yudianto et al. (2021) propose a comprehensive approach to enhancing demand forecasting in the supply chain by utilizing machine learning techniques is shown in figure 13. The objective is to improve forecasting accuracy and efficiency across various sectors, with a specific focus on addressing the gap in the agriculture sector. The proposed system flow involves the utilization of machine learning algorithms, such as neural networks, support vector regression, and others identified through a systematic literature review. By integrating these algorithms into demand forecasting models, the study aims to provide greater accuracy while reducing computational costs compared to traditional methods. The results indicate that machine learning algorithms, particularly neural networks, demonstrate promising performance in demand forecasting across industries.

Figure 13. flowchart of forecasting rainfall and recommending suitable crop varieties

The study emphasizes the need for further research and implementation of machine learning in agriculture to enhance supply chain efficiency and contribute to economic growth, especially in countries such as Indonesia where agriculture plays a significant role in the

national GDP. Overall, the proposed approach highlights the importance of leveraging advanced analytics to optimize supply chain management, thereby facilitating better decision-making and resource allocation.

2.14 Forecasting Mango and Banana Yield of Karnataka, India

Rathod, et al (2021) suggests a hybrid modelling strategy for predicting mango and banana yields in Karnataka, India, with the goal of enhancing prediction accuracy is illustrated in figure 14. This precision is essential for economic planning in the horticulture industry. The study blends linear Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average (ARIMA) models with nonlinear machine learning methods, notably Time Delay Neural Networks (TDNN) and Nonlinear Support Vector Regression (NLSVR). Combining these strategies allows you to capture both linear and nonlinear patterns in data is illustrated in figure 14.

Figure.14. Schematic representation of hybrid methodology

The model is built using historical yield data from 1980 to 2011, and validated using data from 2012 to 2014. The ARIMA model first concentrates on the linear components of the data, while the residuals, which contain nonlinear patterns, are represented using TDNN and NLSVR. These linear and nonlinear models' outputs combine to produce the final yield forecasts. The findings show that hybrid models, specifically the ARIMA-NLSVR combination, outperform single models in both training and testing datasets. The hybrid technique has much reduced Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE) values, indicating higher prediction accuracy. This study demonstrates the efficiency of combining machine learning techniques with traditional time series models to capture the intricacies inherent in agricultural yield data. This dependable forecasting technique helps policymakers and farmers enhance crop management and planning, resulting in economic growth and sustainability in the horticultural sector. The study confirms the practical applicability of hybrid models in agricultural forecasting and encourages their wider application in comparable scenarios. This technique overcomes the constraints of previous models while improving forecast reliability.

2.15A Review on Forecasting Agricultural Demand and Supply with Crop Price Estimation Using Machine Learning Methodologies

Mahore et al (2021) focuses on improving crop yield predictions using machine learning, with a primary emphasis on the Random Forest algorithm is illustrated in figure 15. The objective is to forecast crop yields accurately based on historical agro-climatic data, such as temperature, humidity, pH levels, rainfall, and crop types, thereby aiding agricultural decision-making. The system begins with data collection from sources like Kaggle and Google Weather, covering a decade's worth of data. This is followed by pre-processing, which involves handling missing values, normalizing, and formatting the data. Feature extraction then identifies the most significant predictors, reducing data dimensionality and enhancing model accuracy.

Figure.15. Block diagram of crop yield and demand prediction

The processed data is split into training and testing sets in an 80-20 ratio. The Random Forest algorithm is applied to the training set, chosen for its ability to mitigate over fitting and improve accuracy through the averaging of multiple decision trees. The model's performance is evaluated using metrics such as accuracy and precision, with findings indicating that Random Forest outperforms other algorithms like Support Vector Machine (SVM) and K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN). The study concludes that Random Forest provides the most accurate predictions, making it a valuable tool for forecasting crop yields. This approach supports better crop selection and management, contributing to more efficient agricultural practices and improved economic outcomes for farmers.

The table 1 below provides a summary of existing methods, methodologies used, results, and limitations.

Author	Title	Method	Results	Limitation
Chelliah et al (2024)	Analysis of demand forecasting of agriculture using	CNN	High accuracy (96%)	Model interpretability

	machine learning algorithm			
Mulla et al (2020)	Crop-yield and price forecasting using machine learning	Tree algorithms	high interpretability	Limited to specific crops and environmental conditions
Rasheed et al (2021)	District wise price forecasting of wheat in Pakistan using deep learning	LSTM models	High accuracy	high computational requirements
Alibabaei et al. (2021)	Crop yield estimation using deep learning based on climate big data and irrigation scheduling	BLSTM networks	High accuracy	Data collection from specific locations
Gavahi et al (2021)	DeepYield: A combined convolutional neural network with long short-term memory for crop yield forecasting	ConvLSTM and 3DCNN architectures	Superior performance	High computational complexity
Schwalbert et al (2021)	Satellite-based soybean yield forecast: Integrating machine learning and weather data for improving crop yield prediction in southern Brazil	LSTM networks	High accuracy,	Region-specific (southern Brazil), requires high-quality Satellite data
Tende et al (2023)	Development and Evaluation of a Deep Learning Based System to Predict District-Level Maize Yields in Tanzania	LSTM networks,	high accuracy with low MAPE	Limited to Tanzania, requires continuous data collection
Iatrou et al. (2021)	Topdressing nitrogen demand prediction in rice crop using machine learning systems	XGBoost algorithm	Reduced prediction errors	Specific to nitrogen demand, requires detailed soil data
Kamath et al (2021)	Crop yield forecasting using data mining	Random Forest algorithm	High accuracy (98%)	Focused on historical data
Nazir et al. (2021)	Estimation and forecasting of rice yield using phenology-based algorithm and linear regression model on sentinel-ii Satellite	PLSR, vegetation indices,	High accuracy	Requires high-quality vegetation index data

	data			
Shashidhar. M et al (2021)	Recommendation system for farmers using demand forecasting	Seasonal ARIMA model	Robust statistical methods	Limited to short-term forecasts,
Kamatchi, S. et al (2019)	Improvement of crop production using recommender system by weather forecasts	ANN models	High accuracy (93%)	High computational requirements
Kantasa-Ard et al (2021)	Machine learning for demand forecasting in the physical internet: a case study of agricultural products in Thailand	LSTM model	Improved accuracy with hybrid metaheuristic	Requires detailed parameter tuning
Aamer et al (2021)	Data analytics in the supply chain management: Review of machine learning applications in demand forecasting	Naive Bayes	Effective for agricultural planning	Limited to specific regions, requires detailed historical data
Yudianto et al. (2021)	Rainfall forecasting to recommend crops varieties using moving average and naive bayes methods	Support vector regression for demand forecasting in the supply chain	High accuracy, reduced computational costs	General approach, need for sector-specific adaptations
Rathod, et al (2021)	Forecast mango and banana yields	Hybrid modelling approach using ARIMA with TDNN and NLSVR	Mean Absolute Percentage Error (MAPE)	Complex model integration
Mahore et al (2021)	Crop yield prediction using agro-climatic data	Machine learning approach with Random Forest algorithm	Accuracy, Precision	Dependence on the quality and completeness of input data.

Conclusion

This study thoroughly examines different machine learning and deep learning methods used to predict crop demand. These methods have the potential to revolutionize agricultural planning and decision-making. The study covers a wide range of techniques, including Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) models, Decision Trees, and Random Forest algorithms. These advanced approaches utilize diverse datasets, such as Satellite imagery, weather data, and market trends, to improve prediction accuracy and reliability. The study also underlines the importance of integrating these models with user-friendly applications and interfaces, such as SMS and web-based systems, to make them more practical and useful for farmers and stakeholders. However, there are still issues to resolve, such as data quality, model interpretability, and adaptation to changing market situations. The necessity of region-specific models, as well as the requirement for constant optimization and validation to maintain consistent performance, are also emphasized.

Overall, the findings reveal considerable advances in crop yield and price forecasting, giving vital insights for risk management, resource optimization, and strategic agricultural decision-making. Future research should concentrate on overcoming current limits, improving data integration, and increasing scalability in broader agricultural contexts.

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